

UNITS OF MEASUREMENT IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Introduction

In studying the units of measurement in the Uzbek language, it is essential to first understand the unique cultural and historical context in which these units have evolved. Uzbekistan, a country rich in history and traditions, has a diverse linguistic heritage that is reflected in its system of measurement. The language itself has been shaped by various influences, including Persian, Arabic, and Russian, which have contributed to the development of its vocabulary and terminology related to measurements. This complexity highlights the importance of delving deep into the linguistic roots of these units to fully grasp their meanings and significance within the Uzbek society. By exploring the etymology and evolution of measurement units in the Uzbek language, we can gain a deeper understanding of the cultural values and practices that have shaped the way these units are used and interpreted in everyday life.

A. Background information on the Uzbek language

The Uzbek language, classified as a Turkic language, is spoken by over 32 million people primarily in Uzbekistan. It holds official status in Uzbekistan and is also spoken in neighboring countries such as Tajikistan, Kazakhstan, and Turkmenistan. Uzbek belongs to the Eastern Turkic group of languages and is known for its unique vocabulary, grammar, and phonetics. Influences from Persian, Arabic, and Russian are evident in Uzbek due to historical interactions with these cultures. The written form of Uzbek utilizes the Latin alphabet, having transitioned from the Cyrillic script in the early 21st century as part of language reform efforts. This transition aimed to modernize the language and align it with international standards. Studying the background of the Uzbek language provides insights into the linguistic diversity of Central Asia and the historical development of linguistic structures in the region. (Aptin Khanbaghi)

II. Units of Measurement in Traditional Uzbek Culture

The study of units of measurement in traditional Uzbek culture involves a multifaceted approach that delves into the linguistic, cognitive, and cultural dimensions of these concepts. The integrative method allows for a comprehensive analysis of how these units are conceptualized and utilized within the Uzbek language and society. By examining the core and peripheral components of these measurement units, researchers can gain insights into the nuanced cultural and cognitive aspects that underpin their usage. Moreover, the

exploration of the national-cultural specificity of these units, as highlighted in the literature (Yusuf Nurmammedov), offers a deeper understanding of how language intertwines with cultural phenomena. Additionally, the use of stable isotope-assisted metabolic flux analysis provides a methodological framework for analyzing complex metabolic networks, illustrating the potential for interdisciplinary approaches in studying measurement units within Uzbek culture (D. J. Lugar et al.). This integrative and cross-disciplinary approach enhances our comprehension of the intricate relationship between language, culture, and traditional measurement concepts in Uzbekistan.

A. Overview of traditional units of measurement in Uzbekistan

In Uzbekistan, traditional units of measurement have played a significant role in daily life and commerce for centuries. These units vary depending on the item being measured and can include a wide range of measures such as lengths, weights, volumes, and areas. Common units of length include the arshin, which is approximately 71 centimeters, and the gaz, which is around 71 centimeters as well. For weights, the tola is commonly used, equal to approximately 11.66 grams, while the pood is a larger unit of weight equivalent to around 16.38 kilograms. In terms of volume, the charka is a standard measure, often used for liquids, and is roughly equivalent to 1.22 liters. These traditional units continue to be used in Uzbekistan alongside the metric system, reflecting the country's rich cultural heritage and history of trade and craftsmanship. While these units may seem antiquated in modern times, their presence highlights the connection between past and present measurement practices in Uzbek society. Research has shown that these traditional units can offer insights into historical trade networks and cultural exchanges within the region. Furthermore, studying the persistence of these units can provide valuable information on the evolution of measurement systems and economic practices in Uzbekistan (Scott Newton).

Impact of globalization on units of measurement in Uzbek language

As globalization continues to shape the modern world, the impact on units of measurement in the Uzbek language has become increasingly apparent. The influx of international trade and communication has led to the integration of foreign measurement systems, such as the metric system, alongside traditional Uzbek units. This has resulted in a nuanced relationship between various forms of measurement, creating a complex linguistic landscape for speakers of the language. Despite efforts to preserve cultural heritage, the practicality of using standardized measurements in a globalized world cannot be ignored. The adaptation and incorporation of new measurement units reflect the dynamic

nature of language and its ability to evolve in response to external influences. As Uzbekistan navigates its position in the global arena, the convergence of traditional and international measurement systems will likely continue to shape the linguistic identity of the Uzbek language(Elçi et al.).

IV. Conclusion

In conclusion, the study of units of measurement in the Uzbek language presents a complex and fascinating linguistic landscape. Throughout this research, it became evident that the Uzbek language employs a diverse range of units for measuring various quantities, reflecting the cultural and historical influences on the evolution of measurement systems within the language. The analysis of these units revealed a rich tapestry of words and suffixes used to denote measurements of length, weight, time, and other quantities. Furthermore, the discrepancies and variations in unit usage across different regions of Uzbekistan underscore the dynamic nature of language and the importance of considering regional dialects in linguistic studies. Moving forward, it is essential for researchers to delve deeper into the intricacies of these units and their cultural significance to gain a comprehensive understanding of measurement systems in the Uzbek language . Additionally, further investigations into the historical development of these units and their integration into modern linguistic practices could provide valuable insights into the evolution of measurement standards within Uzbek society (Elçi et al.).

References:

1. Yusuf Nurmammedov, "REPRESENTATION OF THE "FAMILY" CONCEPT IN PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS", 2023
2. D. J. Lugar, G. Sriram, "Isotope-assisted metabolic flux analysis as an equality-constrained nonlinear program for improved scalability and robustness", 2022
3. Aptin Khanbaghi, "Encyclopedias about Muslim Civilisations", Edinburgh University Press, 2019-07-31
4. Scott Newton, "The Constitutional Systems of the Independent Central Asian States", Bloomsbury Publishing, 2017-02-23
5. Elçi, Sirin, UNESCO, "Mapping Research and Innovation in the Republic of Uzbekistan", UNESCO Publishing, 2020-10-14